

Roundtable Discussion: AI in MENA Politics Research

Carolyn Barnett in conversation with Muhammad S. Abdo, Tariq Adely, Cinzia Bianco, Ashrakat Elshehawy, Robert Kubinec, and Michael Robbins

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Introduction, by Carolyn Barnett

For this roundtable, I invited a range of emerging and established scholars who conduct research about and/or use AI in some capacity to share their perspectives on the implications of AI for the future of research on politics in the MENA region and academic research more broadly. I posed questions that asked participants to reflect on lessons learned from their own experiences, potential positive and negative impacts, and hopes and concerns about the future. Contributors submitted their responses in writing, and I have combined them into the following conversation which highlights where their views converge and diverge.

Broadly, most of the contributors are cautiously optimistic about the ability of AI

tools to facilitate working with and deriving insights from large quantities of textual data, ranging from historical records to contemporary media to survey data.

While in part these capabilities will speed up existing research, they also make it possible to undertake analyses that would not have been attempted before because they would have been too time- or labor-intensive. At the same time, contributors are variously wary of the energy demands and ethical implications of AI; the temptation to view LLMs as understanding and synthesizing the true meaning of texts, when this is not what they do; the possibility that existing biases in data will be reproduced and amplified; and the risk that the new relative ease of data analysis will

increase the volume of misleading or downright incorrect claims in circulation.

The conversation is accompanied by a stand-alone essay by Richard Nielsen which argues that Generative AI (GenAI), by streamlining the design and conduct of increasingly advanced quantitative analyses, both frees researchers to spend more time engaged in human-intensive, qualitative data collection and underscores the unique value of interpretive insights generated through direct interaction with the societies we study. While drawing inferences from large quantities of data will be technically easier than ever, deriving meaningful insights from that data will continue to require—and may require more than ever—the expertise and ethnographic sensibilities that researchers hone through personal experience and human interaction, raising the value of these experiences and commitments.

Barnett: What is important to understand about AI itself as we think through its impact on our field?

Kubinec: It is important to be clear about what AI tools are and are not. The building blocks of these models preceded the release of ChatGPT by a significant margin. One core technology, text embeddings, made its way into political science research several years earlier (Gupta et al. 2020; Rodriguez and Spirling 2022; Rodriguez, Spirling, and Stewart 2023). Embeddings are a form of text analysis that is much more nuanced than earlier iterations popular in political science, like structural topic models (Roberts et al. 2014), because embeddings account for both words themselves and their context from many examples of usage. ChatGPT’s model combined text embeddings derived from a massive textual corpus and a model that predicts

natural language responses given prompts. As a result, these large language models (LLMs) can both interpret human input in quantitative terms (embeddings) and create responses by regurgitating relevant passages and words from its training data.

While these technical accomplishments are impressive, especially given the enormous scale of the training data, LLMs are not models of cognition. While many people feel as though they are talking to a sentient being when interacting with an AI bot, that is mainly due to the enormous scope of the data from which its embeddings are derived. As a result, while LLM providers like Anthropic and OpenAI have gone to great lengths to make their software present itself as sentient, these tools have no underlying intelligence. Rather, by projecting most human-written text available into a quantitative format (embeddings) and employing remarkable computational advances (Nvidia’s graphical processing units or GPUs), they can identify relevant texts when prompted with such speed that to a human it appears as if the machine is conversing.

Abdo: Today, when people talk about artificial intelligence, they are often referring to large language models (LLMs). Here’s a way to think about them: In 1941, the Argentine writer Jorge Luis Borges published his short story *The Library of Babel*. In it, Borges depicts the universe as an infinite library housing every possible arrangement of 25 characters. The central idea of the story emerges from this premise: if every possible arrangement of these characters does exist somewhere, then the library must contain not only countless meaningless books but also every meaningful book that has been written or could ever be written. The library is both omniscient and indifferent in such a way as

to leave its librarians wandering in perpetual uncertainty about where meaning lies.

LLMs are, in many ways, the technological realization of this premise. Trained on massive corpora that approximate the library's totality, even though they do not “know” in any human sense, they still can reproduce linguistic patterns with enough fluency to simulate understanding. These models move through *the library* far more quickly than humans, but they are still tied to the same deeper uncertainty about meaning, truth, and the limits of interpretation.

Barnett: What is one way you have used AI in your research to date, and what is one reason you have been cautious about or skeptical of applying AI tools in your work?

Abdo: Over the past decade, artificial intelligence has occupied a central place in my formal research agenda. My research typically involves curating datasets that support the development, evaluation, and critical analysis of language technologies while also fine-tuning LLMs to better handle domain-specific and linguistically complex tasks. And since the advent of LLMs, I have collaborated with colleagues on building several AI systems across different domains. For example, in AMWAL (Abdo et al. 2025), a project focused on Arabic financial news, we developed a first-of-its-kind model capable of automatically detecting and classifying key financial entities and events, including companies, financial instruments, and products, which is an essential task for structuring unorganized financial text into analyzable data. We also worked on a project designed to help AI systems distinguish between 18 Arabic dialects, a task that remains especially difficult because of Arabic's rich and complex morphology.

However, despite my extensive involvement in AI research, I have approached its applications with a degree of caution and skepticism. In addition to the many problems that I have witnessed first-hand while working with LLMs—such as the risk of bias and inequity in datasets, hallucination issues, ethical and privacy challenges, and lack of interpretability—I remain cautious about the sustainability and scalability of these technologies. The major concern hinges on the intensive and expensive computational demands of training and deploying such models, which raise significant environmental and accessibility issues. This is because training large models demands prohibitive amounts of Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) time that is equivalent to months of household energy use (Strubell et al. 2018; Champion 2023), which compounds the challenge for countries in the MENA region where the necessary technologies remain largely inaccessible. This escalating drain on resources increases the carbon footprint of AI, which is already on par with entire sectors like aviation (Jackson & Hodgkinson 2022) and presents numerous challenges to global sustainability goals.

These bottlenecks become even more pronounced in low-resource environments where deploying these models on mobile devices yields real-time performance that often falters due to scalability-related deficiencies. For instance, when deploying a lightweight transformer-based model on a mid-range Android device, response delays can exceed several seconds per query, which renders the tool unusable for real-time applications. This forces developers to either compromise on model capability or depend on cloud connectivity, an assumption that remains unrealistic in areas with limited or unstable Internet infrastructure. These challenges may exacerbate economic disparities in multiple ways,

including favoring well-funded institutions and limiting access for researchers in developing countries. AI also introduces opportunity costs. Efforts to build AI capabilities may divert attention from viable alternatives to AI, such as human-led data curation, which may offer more equitable and less resource-intensive trajectories.

Adely: My primary engagement with artificial intelligence (AI) technologies has come in the context of fieldwork. In my research, I use ethnographic methods to examine how differently situated workers produce, adapt, and deploy AI models for Arabic, focusing on the information technology (IT) sector in Amman, Jordan, a regional outsourcing destination for technical and linguistic labor. While conducting fieldwork from 2023 to 2025, I regularly tested AI language models and their updates, carried out participant observation at startups utilizing AI technologies, and took courses about building and fine-tuning AI models. Experimenting with these models—and reflecting on those interactions—was central to understanding how my interlocutors made, and made sense of, these emerging technologies. My work shows how ideological claims about Arabic and long-standing linguistic hierarchies shape AI models, political economies, and labor arrangements.

Outside of these fieldwork contexts, I have largely minimized my use of AI technologies, aside from a small number of proofreading tools (e.g., Grammarly) and scholarship search engines (e.g., Research Rabbit) billed as “AI-powered.” Despite—or, more likely, because of—my research on these models, I remain skeptical about their applications for data collection, analysis, and text generation. AI technologies raise a variety of ethical questions: the environmental impacts of

training and maintaining models (see Wu et al. 2022 for an overview); the exploitative labor practices underpinning their production (Gray 2019; Kirk 2025); and the wholesale scraping of academic knowledge to train and monetize these models (Gibney 2024). The key source of my skepticism, however, relates to the technological logics underpinning today’s generative AI models, including large language models (LLMs) like OpenAI’s GPTs, Gemini, and Claude. Put simply, the capacity of these AI technologies to generate text and speech that mimic human communication resides in their ability to predict what “token,” a unit of textual data, will most likely follow in a sequence, given the surrounding context. As AI engineers often put it during interviews: models are very good at guessing the next word.

The fact that AI’s “generative” capabilities rest in predicting the most likely response, reflecting countless past examples in its training dataset, casts a shadow over its potential for scholarly work. I would also suggest that this concern is especially pronounced for scholarship on the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), given the long history of essentializing frameworks and narratives applied to political, cultural, and social life in the region (see Wedeen 2002 on cultural essentialism; also Lockman 2010; Said 1979). This is not to say that we ought to turn away from artificial intelligence—as a technology, a discourse, and a driver of shifting political-economic relations—in our research on the region. It is reshaping labor dynamics, state-society relations, policing, surveillance and countless other domains of social, political, and economic life. But as a technology whose outputs reproduce an archive of previous utterances, I am not optimistic about its potential to advance social scientific scholarship at the current moment—particularly from and about

the MENA.

Elshehawy: One fast-growing use of LLMs in political science is text classification and annotation (Gilardi, Alizadeh, and Kubli 2023; Törnberg 2025). In recent ongoing work, my coauthors and I used a large language model (GPT-4o) to classify approximately one million police press releases issued by local police stations across Germany over a decade (Elshehawy et al. 2025). One of our main goals was to identify whether each press release contained out-group cues: explicit or implicit references to a suspect's foreign nationality or ethnicity. This is the kind of classification task where LLMs can be useful. The corpus was massive and unstructured, authored by different press officers, and the information we needed to extract was often conveyed through subtle, contextual language rather than consistent keywords. Dictionary-based approaches and some of the conventional Natural Language Processing tools would likely miss part of what mattered, especially where cues were implicit and context-dependent. LLMs allowed us to capture implicit meaning at scale.

The classification challenge we faced (large-volume, unstructured, context-dependent text) is one that many MENA researchers will recognize. Whether the source material is Arabic-language media archives or historical documents, the core problem is the same: extracting structured information from messy text where meaning is often embedded in context rather than stated outright. LLMs can be well-suited to this kind of task, especially when the target concept is context-de-

pendent.

But, of course, the promise of LLM tools has to come with careful thinking about how to validate their output. It is important to think carefully about the prompt engineering phase. Small changes in prompt wording can meaningfully shift classification output. Sensitivity to prompt variation should be tested and carefully considered (Halterman and Keith 2025). A good practice is for researchers to validate the LLM output against a hand-coded gold standard and report full performance metrics: F1 scores, precision, and recall, not just overall accuracy.¹ Overfitting is a risk when prompts are iteratively refined. Validation on a hold-out set not used during prompt development guards against this. Finally, as part of validation, it is useful to assess inter-coder reliability among human coders and agreement between human coders and the LLM. This allows researchers to check if the LLM judgments align with those of trained annotators, while recognizing that agreement alone is not sufficient evidence of validity. These are some of the common validation practices, but the methodological literature in this area is expanding fast and worth keeping up with.

In sum, LLMs make it increasingly feasible to extract structured information from the large, often unstructured corpora that are common in MENA research, but their use also makes careful validation especially important.

¹ Precision measures the proportion of all positive classifications of the model that are in fact positive
Precision = (True Positive)/(True Positive+False Positive)

Recall measures the proportion of all actual positive cases that were classified by the model accurately as positives

Recall = (True Positive)/(True Positive+False Negative)

The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

Kubinec: I have mainly employed these tools in my own research to take care of technical clerical tasks and machine translation. For my research, this involves deriving code for a variety of projects from cleaning data to running complex online surveys. The code generation capabilities of LLMs are quite useful because they can respond to natural language prompts; this means that I can express what code I want in colloquial language that the model can then interpret as code. Similarly, most LLMs seem to excel at translation—which is in a sense what they are doing when converting a text prompt into a programming language. In fact, some of the most useful tasks have involved prompting an LLM to input Arabic text directly into computer code, which is a very difficult thing to do given the right-to-left versus left-to-right differences in Arabic typography and code.

I put LLMs to the test in a recent project with Aseem Mahajan (King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals) in which we collected a dataset of over 1 million advertisements on Facebook that contained climate change-related content. We prompted the LLM to identify any content that could be described as “greenwashing”, i.e., including misleading statements about an organization’s impacts on climate. We employed a set of six open-source LLMs for this task to compare performance. Again, thanks to the LLM’s remarkable translation capabilities, we were able to conduct this exercise in more than ten languages (including Arabic)—which would be beyond the capabilities of most research teams.

While we found that the LLMs did identify useful information, in total their performance relative to humans was mediocre (Kubinec and Mahajan 2025). The LLMs classified about one-third of the ads as containing

greenwashing content whereas our human coders found only 2-3%. However, by combining our LLM coding with other indicators derived from the ads, we were able to use a quantitative measurement model to extract information about greenwashing from the noisy responses. The LLMs did improve our project, especially as human coding for a database of this size was not trivial. However, robust assessment was necessary to avoid making vastly over-confident coding decisions from the LLMs alone.

Robbins: The clearest use to date of AI in the research of Arab Barometer, where I serve as Project Director, has been to help us write code and summarize data. Each wave of Arab Barometer requires us to write thousands of lines of code to conduct quality control and produce data visualizations in our standard branding, for example. Much of this work, such as the code needed to produce a topline, is fairly rote in nature but can take a significant amount of time. We have therefore explored using AI to produce initial code in some cases.

Second, we have used AI to generate preliminary summaries of findings on specific topics or questions. AI can take results and quickly produce an overall summary or compare findings to previous waves without requiring us to manually enter all of the results.

The key limitation we have found so far is that AI frequently makes minor errors. None of the code it has written runs without corrections or adjustments by our researchers. Additionally, AI has not always reported results fully accurately in its summaries, requiring careful fact-checking of its findings. In short, any task we have asked AI to perform still requires detailed and engaged review. Still, it has been helpful in increasing the efficiency with which we use and dig into the

project's findings.

Barnett: What is one exciting opportunity you think AI presents for Middle East researchers? How can researchers responsibly take advantage of this opportunity?

Abdo: When considering what AI has to offer researchers in the MENA region, we often think first about its promise for accelerating large-scale data analysis, surveying the literature, and streamlining time-intensive research tasks. Yet for humanities-oriented research, AI may also present an even more consequential possibility: affirming and amplifying the institutional relevance of the humanities by making humanistic expertise central to the design, evaluation, and governance of language technologies. There is a need for MENA-focused humanities scholars to play such a role: current LLMs are not culturally neutral. Studies have shown that widely used models often reproduce value patterns associated with English-speaking and European contexts, while Arabic-focused and multilingual models can also display bias toward Western-associated entities and stereotypes (Navigli, Conia, and Ross 2023; Naous et al. 2024; Tao et al. 2024).

Meanwhile, the humanities have been under pressure not just rhetorically but institutionally. Humanities disciplines in the Middle East face declining prestige, reduced funding, deteriorating infrastructure, and worsening labor conditions. In Egypt, the different fields of humanities have been suffering from poor student-to-faculty ratios and lower social valuation than disciplines such as medicine or engineering. These pressures paint a concrete picture of a compounding crisis, where institutional strain and social devaluation operate in tandem (Fahmy 2017; Hodapp 2022). These concerns have not been voiced by

researchers alone. In Egypt, they have also appeared at the level of state discourse. In April 2025, President Sisi questioned the value of fields such as arts, commerce, and law and urged families toward programming, communications, and AI-related paths. Later, in March 2026, he called for an end to majors with no clear employment prospects. The policy was later clarified by the Chair of the Parliamentary Committee on Education and Scientific Research, and former Egyptian Minister of Higher Education, as not a full abolition of humanities fields, but a reduction in admissions to disciplines seen as misaligned with labor-market demand (Aham Online 2023; Mamdouh 2026; Ahmed 2026). This may open a space for interested humanities scholars, such as linguists, historians, philosophers, and area specialists, to demonstrate how their expertise can contribute to the development of AI. They can work on defining what culturally valid evaluation benchmarks look like, curating archives and corpora, and developing new curricula in areas such as AI safety and AI governance.

Elshehawy: The opportunity I find exciting is the potential of multimodal AI to unlock sources, such as archival records, historical documents, maps, and administrative data, that have long been difficult to analyze at scale. Multimodal AI refers to systems that can work across multiple data types, such as images and text. Conventional optical character recognition has struggled with aspects of Arabic-script text for a long time (especially for handwritten or degraded documents); the cursive nature of the script, variation in diacritical marking, and font diversity have made reliable automated transcription elusive. Recent advances in multimodal LLMs represent a step forward. This is a rapidly expanding area of research. Models are increasingly capable of reading not just printed

Arabic, but also some handwritten manuscripts, although limitations remain across domains, layouts, and complex document formats (Heakl et al. 2025).

For MENA researchers, this matters because vast quantities of source material exist only as physical documents or image scans. Newspaper archives, court records, and administrative files across the region remain locked in formats that have long been difficult to analyze at scale. AI-powered Optical Character Recognition (OCR) can change that.

The implications for historical political economy research, for example, are profound. Multimodal AI could make it increasingly feasible to build larger and more systematic datasets from archival sources, tracing patterns of landholding, endowment activity, and institutional change across locations and over time. The methods can advance research on questions related to land inequality, institutional persistence, state-building, taxation, and state-society relations; especially as multimodal LLMs continue to extend the reach of computational tools to handwritten and archival materials that have so far been difficult to process at scale.

Of course, this also raises questions about the verification of these methods. The use of multimodal AI for Arabic-script OCR and archival data extraction is an expanding field. Sample-based human verification against original documents is important, particularly for degraded or ambiguous passages where models are most likely to err. Rather than treating all model output as equally reliable, workflows should flag low-confidence extractions. Important metrics depend on the use case, but may include character error rates and word error rates, among others. Researchers should also report limitations,

documenting, where possible, error rates by script type, document condition, and historical period. Ideally, domain experts—such as historians, paleographers, and linguists with deep knowledge of the source material—would be part of the verification loop. Scholars trained in the relevant traditions can catch the kinds of errors that would aggregate into misleading datasets.

AI tools can open archival documents and resources that have not been accessible. For MENA researchers, this is a genuinely exciting moment, but like any other empirical method, the quality of what we build with these tools depends on how carefully we validate the outputs.

Robbins: As someone engaged in a project involving a large amount of data, I think one of the most exciting opportunities AI presents is the possibility of improving how we process, compare, and learn from the data we collect. A major challenge for Arab Barometer is managing this large volume of information. Survey research in the Middle East often involves substantial complexity. One of the Arab Barometer’s central goals is to enable cross-national comparison while taking individual country contexts into account. Its ability to process vast amounts of data could help us more efficiently collect and analyze survey material that is often underused, especially open-ended responses, interviewer notes, and other paradata collected during interviews. To date, we have limited the number of open-ended response items in part because of the challenge of coding them on the back end. AI tools could also help us identify latent themes across countries and survey waves.

But these possibilities also come with challenges. The data we collect are produced through careful instrument design,

interviewer training, sampling decisions, and context-sensitive fieldwork. AI can assist with some parts of this process, but it cannot replace the detailed knowledge necessary to conduct survey research, use survey data, and accurately interpret the nuances of public opinion surveys. Doing so requires highly specialized knowledge, a detailed understanding of both the region and public opinion, and a strong grasp of the survey research process. My recommendation would be for those engaged in survey research or similar projects to use AI cautiously as a support for quality control and exploratory analysis. The key principle is that AI may help scale parts of the survey research process and make them more efficient, but it cannot replace the careful methodological labor that makes survey inference valid in the first place.

Bianco: One important opportunity AI presents for Middle East researchers lies in the ability to work at scale while remaining attentive to context. Research on the region has long been shaped by the dispersion of relevant material across languages, institutions, and extended time horizons. Political communication, legal texts, media coverage, and official statements are historically difficult to analyze systematically. As a consequence, research agendas have frequently followed what is most visible or readily accessible rather than what is most analytically significant (Anderson 2006).

Large language models (LLMs) make it possible to assemble and navigate large textual corpora without requiring early narrowing of the research question. They can summarize long documents, support semantic search across multilingual corpora, and identify recurring themes across thousands of texts. For policy archives, legal documents, and media databases, this substantially lowers the cost of

entry and enables more systematic exploration. It also creates space for more transparent workflows, as researchers can retain clear links between analytical claims and specific documents or passages. This allows scholars to begin with a broader view of the informational environment and then determine where close reading and deeper interpretation are most needed. Rather than relying primarily on small samples or emblematic cases, researchers can trace patterns of repetition, framing, and omission across time and across institutions. This is particularly valuable for the study of incremental change. For example, shifts in policy language or elite priorities often unfold gradually and can be difficult to detect through conventional sampling strategies.

Responsible use depends on treating AI as an assistive instrument rather than as an interpretive authority. Models can help identify where patterns appear stable and where they shift, but they cannot determine why those patterns matter. Responsibility lies in ensuring that interpretation and judgment remain grounded in regional knowledge, triangulation, and transparent documentation of how models were used. AI can expand the range of material that can be examined, but credible research still requires clear reasoning about what the data can and cannot show (Anderson 2006).

Kubinec: Arguably, the most useful aspect of LLMs for research in the MENA region is its ability to easily handle multilingual texts. As many researchers know, Arabic/Farsi/Hebrew/Turkish translation, especially at any scale, is no easy feat, and as a result, scholars tend to rely more on English-language sources about the region (Fahmy 2026; Nielsen and Zhou 2025; Di Bitetti and Ferreras 2017). LLMs' facility with translation, not just with

readable text but also more difficult formats like PDFs and images, can help render much of the non-Western world legible to those without a native-level language facility. Similarly, and perhaps more importantly, LLMs permit researchers without English fluency to prepare monographs for submission to English-language journals much more easily. Ideally, LLMs can provide a boost to the Arabic, Hebrew, Persian, and Turkish languages by reducing pressures to read and write exclusively in English—though I think scholars should still write in their own language first and translate the content rather than relying on LLMs to produce an article wholesale.

Of course, as mentioned previously, there is danger in relying on LLMs for the purposes of cognition. LLMs do not think and consequently cannot produce anything truly original. The risk of over-reliance on translation tools could degrade linguistic fluency, which is particularly worrying for scholars from the Anglophone world. My advice for scholars is to consider investing more time, not less, in reading and writing in the spoken languages of the region. As AI tools hopefully take over time-intensive tasks like data cleaning and rote translation, consider investing that time into more fieldwork, interviews, and exploratory reading. In other words, by employing LLMs to take on tasks that require little thought, scholars can (hopefully) find more time for open-ended research that involves creativity and higher-level thinking.

Another note of caution for scholars is to remember the risk of dependence on commercial tools as core parts of the research process. Part of the reason that we employed open-source LLMs for our study of Facebook ads was due to reproducibility problems with commercial providers like ChatGPT, which can suddenly disappear models (Barrie,

Palmer, and Spirling 2024). Scholars should have backup strategies for prompts, conversations, and output derived from any closed-source LLMs. Furthermore, it should go without saying that all LLM output should be checked—these are at bottom statistical models, and their flexibility means that they will always have some probability of providing incorrect output (i.e., hallucinations). Rigorous research still requires rigor, and only human beings can decide whether an analysis' claims are in fact valid.

Barnett: Some researchers, both within MENA and beyond, are exploring the possibility that “synthetic participants” (AI agents developed based on information about local populations' demographics) could be used to pilot surveys, test behavioral interventions, or otherwise facilitate research where access to populations is expensive, dangerous, or logistically difficult. To what extent do you think this is a promising or concerning development?

Adely: I consider “synthetic participants” a concerning development, especially given the opacity of AI models. The most prominent language models in circulation today (e.g., OpenAI's GPT models, Gemini, Claude) are built on closed-source, proprietary training data. Even some ostensibly “open-source” models disclose their code but not training datasets (e.g., Meta's LLaMA). Model makers might disclose the types of data used, such as large-scale scraping of text from the Internet. While there is little available data on Internet traffic and content produced from the MENA, it is telling that Arabic, Farsi, and Turkish only constitute around 3 percent of the Internet's linguistic landscape (W3Techs 2026). Second, the risks associated with this opacity are further accentuated by the common practice of using synthetic data for

contexts in which data is scarce or cost-prohibitive (Fitzgerald 2024). This would mean constructing synthetic participants on a foundation of synthetic data to design research instruments and projects to capture the experiences and perspectives of communities in the MENA. Finally, even in an (unlikely) scenario where a researcher could review and evaluate training data, the mechanisms through which models train are not fully explainable. This is not to suggest that AI technologies are a complete black box; as Salvaggio (2025) notes, “they associate words in a vast vector space, and we can trace likely word pairings. What remains opaque is how specific correlations are inferred from vast training data.” Together, these compounding layers of opacity make the prospect of integrating synthetic participants into research alarming.

Emerging technologies do offer possibilities for conducting research among populations and locales where fieldwork raises safety and ethical concerns. The COVID-19 pandemic prompted further development and adoption of digital methods from remote interviewing to online ethnographies. While they expand possibilities for research, these methods certainly bring with them ethical, political, and methodological issues; yet, I consider them more promising than “synthetic participants” as a way of connecting with and adapting to the realities of our field sites and communities.

Bianco: The use of synthetic participants is promising in limited and clearly defined ways. As tools for piloting surveys, testing question wording, or identifying implicit assumptions in research design, they can help researchers avoid basic errors before engaging real populations. In this role, they can improve research design by revealing ambiguity, cultural misalignment, or unintended leading

effects in prompts. They may also help anticipate how different framings could be received before significant resources are committed to fieldwork.

Concerns arise when synthetic participants are treated as substitutes for empirical engagement. These agents do not represent lived experience. They reproduce patterns present in existing data. In the Middle East, where documentation is uneven and often filtered through official or elite channels, this limitation is particularly consequential. Groups that are hardest to access are often those least represented in training data, meaning that synthetic participants may appear most confident precisely where their grounding is weakest. Using synthetic participants to generate substantive findings, therefore, risks reinforcing existing blind spots. Simulation can reproduce the assumptions embedded in available texts rather than the realities of populations whose voices are limited or strategically absent. For this reason, synthetic participants are best confined to instrument development rather than treated as evidence.

Robbins: The use of synthetic respondents might have some value for tasks such as checking the logic of a pilot survey or running other basic simulations. However, I would not advise using such agents for the other purposes mentioned here. Arab Barometer’s experience underscores that public opinion in the region cannot be reduced to demographic profiles. What respondents say is shaped not only by age, gender, education, or place of residence, but also by political context, trust, timing, interviewer effects, local conditions, and perceptions of risk. In any setting, but especially in MENA, respondents may conceal preferences, offer strategically cautious answers, or interpret politically sensitive questions in context-dependent ways.

Synthetic participants are poorly equipped to capture these dynamics precisely because they are built from generalized patterns rather than actual realities on the ground.

Having worked on Arab Barometer for the last two decades, I continue to be struck by the extent to which the data still produce major surprises. Commonly, correlations we expect to find do not appear, while other unexpected correlations emerge, or a long-standing trend reverses. Frequently, this happens not only in a single country but across the entire wave. As we dig more deeply into the data, we arrive at a much more nuanced understanding of political behavior in MENA and how ordinary people understand their worlds. Without measuring these concepts with human participants, we would surely miss these important findings. This reality points to the methodological danger that synthetic participants will inherit the blind spots of the data used to build them. Results from Arab Barometer are collected in a specific context at a specific time. We design questions to be less sensitive to day-to-day events, but we cannot fully prevent current events from influencing responses of those interviewed. Building synthetic populations from existing survey data or other measures of public opinion will likely replicate existing distortions. Moreover, given how limited the available data on populations living in MENA are compared with many other regions, existing biases may be especially misleading and could yield results that are counterproductive for researchers. At this point, I do not believe that the potential benefits outweigh the potential costs of using synthetic participants to try to measure public opinion in MENA.

Barnett: To what extent does the use of AI risk biasing inferences about the region toward more “data-rich” and AI-forward con-

texts like the GCC? What could be done to mitigate this bias?

Abdo: Aggregation bias could mean that the MENA region’s AI-driven future may be disproportionately shaped by a few data-rich hubs. This disparity of resources is confirmed by The Government AI Readiness Index, which ranks countries based on their capacity to deploy AI in public services, which notes that MENA has the widest performance gap of any global region. For example, the United Arab Emirates scores 72.36 and Saudi Arabia 71.57, while Syria and Yemen trail at 21.72 and 14.48, respectively. This clear divide reflects profound inequalities in infrastructure and digital investment (Oxford Insights 2025). This unevenness is further reinforced by the sheer scale of investment flowing into the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). Saudi Arabia’s \$40 billion HUMAN initiative and the UAE’s backing of ventures such as MGX and G42, reflect a level of capital commitment that few other states in the region can match.

Bianco: Evaluating AI systems trained on GCC-related data gives away their limitations immediately to the expert eye. These systems tend to privilege environments that are digitally legible and well-documented. Within the Middle East, this creates a structural pull toward the Gulf, where official communication is abundant, standardized, and frequently available in global languages. As a result, AI-assisted research risks overrepresenting these contexts while underweighting others. This shows up most clearly in their interpretation of stability and risk. A system exposed primarily to large volumes of consistent, institutionally produced text may learn that stability is the baseline and that political change is unlikely, not because it has understood political dynamics, but because the

data it encounters is unusually uniform. Models trained in these environments often underestimate the possibility of change.

Preventing false confidence requires interventions at both the training and evaluation stages. Training data should be diversified to include sources that differ structurally from official narratives and that introduce variation across time, topic, and institutional voice. Evaluation should explicitly test for overconfidence, including whether models can flag ambiguity and avoid treating absence of evidence as evidence of absence. In high-stakes applications, human review remains essential when model confidence is high, but the underlying data stream is narrow or tightly controlled. In such settings, confidence itself should be treated as a potential risk signal rather than reassurance (King, Pan, and Roberts 2013; Xia et al. 2025).

Furthermore, researchers can deliberately incorporate lower-visibility sources and treat gaps and silences as analytically meaningful. What remains crucial is to be explicit about the scope of inference. When conclusions are driven primarily by data-rich contexts, this should be acknowledged as a limitation and, where relevant, interpreted as part of the region's political economy of information (Anderson 2006).

Barnett: What is one thing that concerns you about how AI might impact research in our field? What can be done to address this concern?

Adely: In the past several years, I have noticed a concerning trend of conflating technology's multilingual capabilities with its capacity to reflect diverse viewpoints. If a model can produce Arabic (or Farsi, Kurdish, and Turkish for that matter), the logic goes,

then the model can speak to cultural, social, and political life in the Arab world. In many ways, this trend reflects a broader issue with generative AI: the ability to generate language that convincingly mimics human communication becomes a proxy for claims about a model's intelligence, understanding, and reasoning (Bender and Koller 2020).

The conflation of language with meaning, understanding, and/or knowledge is especially fraught in the context of "low-resource" languages, linguistic varieties for which there exist comparatively few datasets and computational resources. For example, in the early months of my fieldwork in fall 2023, a recurrent topic of conversation with my interlocutors was the recent release of an LLM by a UAE-based company, which promoted their product as the most advanced model to date for Arabic. At tech forums and conferences across Amman, a regular refrain was the need for "Arab AI" that reflected Arab values, culture, and political-ethical commitments, as opposed to the "Western" perspective perceived to be embedded in AI tools like ChatGPT.

This Emirati model seemed poised to address these calls. Trained on a bilingual dataset (Arabic and English), the company's promotional materials boasted about training the model on over 100 billion Arabic tokens, or roughly one-third of the total training data. As I tested the model—on my own and alongside engineers and other workers with AI expertise—I could appreciate the model's ability to produce grammatically sound and contextually relevant statements in Arabic. (In 2023, just a year after ChatGPT's initial public release, the ability to effectively generate Arabic text was still quite novel). However, the Arabic-language data on which the model was trained was likely—at least par-

tially—machine-translated (see Sadallah et al. 2025 on the pitfalls of machine-translated data for Arabic). The anecdotes, references, and names in the model's outputs, while communicated in Arabic, suggested a reliance on data that was originally in English, reflecting a different set of social, cultural, and political assumptions. In sum, this conflation of localized language capabilities with localized understanding and meaning does not reflect how AI tools function, and this disparity is especially pronounced for the language contexts in which scholars of MENA work.

In terms of addressing this concern, there is no simple solution. At one level, it entails a critical eye toward information produced by AI models, even those with the capacity to produce the language varieties used in our field sites. More broadly, as AI technologies become more thoroughly imbricated in our field sites, I see the need for a renewed commitment to methods and methodologies that consider how utterances and symbols can reflect a wide range of meanings (Wedeen 2002). Just as we remain attentive to the gap between what research participants say and what they do or believe, we must bring a critical eye toward the possibility that participant responses, institutional statements, and publicly available data may be mediated by AI tools in ways that obscure social and political realities.

Bianco: A central concern is that AI may increase the risk of false confidence, as I noted above. LLMs are optimized to produce fluent and internally coherent outputs. When applied to political text, that fluency can be mistaken for accuracy or completeness. Consistency in the available data does not necessarily correspond to genuine consensus. This concern echoes long-standing debates in Middle East politics. Apparent stability in

authoritarian systems has often reflected active management rather than deep agreement, and periods of robustness have obscured underlying vulnerabilities (Bellin 2012). Moreover, political meaning frequently emerges from euphemism, selective emphasis, or omission. Dialectal variation and context-specific references further complicate automated parsing. Models may process such material smoothly while missing what experienced readers recognize as the central signal. In addition, many regional corpora are shaped by uneven digitization, inconsistent metadata, and shifting platform practices, which can introduce hidden measurement error.

Addressing these concerns requires methodological caution. Automated text analysis requires validation and human judgment to support credible inference (Grimmer and Stewart 2013). In practice, this involves assessing whether results hold across different source types, languages, and time periods, and being explicit about uncertainty. Recent AI research reinforces this point by showing that models frequently produce confident outputs even when they are wrong, and that verbal confidence should not be equated with reliability (Xia et al. 2025; Groot and Valdenegro-Toro 2024). For politically sensitive research, a useful discipline is to treat model confidence as a signal for further scrutiny rather than as a conclusion. Embedding these practices into research design can allow AI to support more careful scholarship rather than more persuasive errors (Grimmer and Stewart 2013).

Robbins: My major concern is that we will see an overreliance on AI to do work that is best left to a careful researcher. Good research is difficult and tedious and requires extremely detailed attention. There is a

natural tendency to try to speed up this process, particularly when working with large and complex datasets. In the case of public opinion research in particular, the use of AI could be especially troubling because much of what appears straightforward in a dataset is actually fragile and conditional. Responses depend on question wording, interview context, social desirability pressures, political conditions, and whether respondents trust that their answers are confidential. These issues are important in any context, but in many parts of the Middle East and North Africa, they are major considerations and are central to how survey responses should be interpreted.

Even before the rise of AI, I saw many analyses that did not sufficiently take these factors into account. I am deeply concerned that AI will make this problem more common by making data processing and analysis appear more straightforward than they really are. Researchers may be tempted to use models to classify attitudes, infer ideology, or summarize open-ended responses without adequately considering the conditions under which those responses were produced. The result could be a larger number of analyses using public opinion data, but also a larger number that misinterpret the results or are based on spurious correlations.

Ultimately, researchers cannot simply outsource research to AI. AI will not be able to compensate for poor questionnaire design, a weak sample design, translation problems, or a lack of understanding of the survey research process. As a result, researchers should be cautious in their use of AI and use it only to facilitate research, as opposed to expecting it to do the research itself. Most importantly, researchers must think carefully through research design and the patterns most likely

to account for the distributions they observe in the data. For example, if AI identifies what appears to be a novel finding in public opinion, that pattern must be checked very carefully against established measures, country expertise, and, where possible, subsequent survey rounds or qualitative evidence, just as it should be if AI had not been used. However, given the vast amounts of data that AI can process, the risks are far greater than before of generating meaningless correlations that could be advanced as new theories to explain attitudes and behavior in MENA. ♦

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